

Appendix

Table 1. Features' Rank According to the mRMR Method

GPS and descriptive parameters used in this study, and selected by the low-variance method and sorted according to the mRMR method rank (first column), after using the *k*-means clustering algorithm.

Rank	Feature name	Rank	Feature name
1	Player Corridor 1*	131	Velocity Band 2 Total Duration
2	Player Position 5*	132	Player Load Per Minute
3	Type of Session*	133	Velocity Band 2 Total Distance
4	Competition NOS*	134	Velocity Band 1 Total Distance
5	Velocity Band 3 Recovery Band 5 Total No. Efforts	135	Velocity Band 4 Distance Band 4 Total No. Efforts
6	Player Position 2*	136	Acceleration Band 5 Distance %
7	Day Week 4*	137	Velocity Band 5 Distance Band 3 Total No. Efforts
8	Acceleration Band 5 Average Duration	138	Velocity Band 5 Recovery Band 5 Total No. Efforts
9	Player Position 6*	139	Player Load (Slow)
10	Day Week 6*	140	Player Load Band 5 Total Distance
11	Velocity Band 4 Max Effort Distance	141	IMA Impacts Band 5 Count
12	Result 3.0*	142	Total Acceleration Load
13	Day Week 3*	143	Acceleration Band 4 Total Effort Count
14	Acceleration Band 5 Average Distance	144	Velocity Band 4 Total Effort Count
15	Day Week 5*	145	Acceleration Band 4 Duration %
16	Peak Player Load	146	Acceleration Band 2 Total Distance
17	Acceleration Band 4 Average Duration	147	Velocity Band 4 Distance Band 3 Total No. Efforts
18	Player Corridor 2*	148	Acceleration Band 1 Total Effort Count
19	Player Position 3*	149	Velocity Band 5 Distance Band 2 Total No. Efforts
20	Player Load Band 2 Average Effort Count	150	Velocity Band 3 Total Effort Count
21	Result 1.0*	151	Player Load Band 4 Distance %
22	Result 0.0*	152	Velocity Band 2 Total Effort Count
23	Acceleration Band 4 Average Effort Count	153	Profile Max Velocity
24	IMA Impacts Band 6 Count	154	IMA Impacts Band 1 Count
25	Average Distance	155	Velocity Band 2 Recovery Band 1 Total No. Efforts
26	Velocity Band 1 Average Duration	156	Player Load Band 4 Average Distance
27	Acceleration Band 4 Average Distance	157	Metabolic Power Band 1 Total Duration
28	Player Load Band 1 Average Distance	158	Velocity Band 6 Max Effort Distance
29	Velocity Band 3 Recovery Band 3 Total No. Efforts	159	Acceleration Band 5 Total Effort Count
30	Day Week 2*	160	Max Vel (% Max)
31	Average Player Load (1D Up)	161	Player Load Band 3 Distance %
32	Acceleration Band 5 Average Effort Count	162	IMA Impacts Band 2 Average Count
33	IMA Impacts Band 6 Average Count	163	Velocity Band 5 Max Effort Distance
34	Average Player Load	164	Acceleration Band 5 Duration %
35	Velocity Band 1 Average Distance	165	Acceleration Band 3 Total Effort Count
36	Average Player Load (1D Side)	166	Player Load Band 3 Total Effort Count
37	RHIE Bout Recovery - Max	167	Player Load Band 2 Distance %
38	Velocity Band 4 Average Distance	168	Velocity Band 6 Average Effort Count
39	Velocity Band 2 Average Duration	169	Player Load (1D Fwd %)
40	Average Player Load (1D Fwd)	170	Player Load Band 5 Average Effort Count
41	Velocity Band 4 Average Duration	171	Player Load Band 2 Duration %
42	Velocity Band 2 Average Distance	172	Player Load Band 3 Total Distance
43	Player Load Band 2 Average Duration	173	Acceleration Band 4 Distance %
44	Average Player Load (Slow)	174	Velocity Band 3 Recovery Band 1 Total No. Efforts
45	Velocity Band 3 Average Duration	175	Acceleration Band 1 Average Distance
46	Player Load Band 2 Average Distance	176	Duration (m)*
47	IMA Impacts Band 3 Average Count	177	Player Load Band 5 Total Effort Count

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Rank	Feature name	Rank	Feature name
48	Velocity Band 4 Recovery Band 5 Total No. Efforts	178	Acceleration Band 3 Total Distance
49	Velocity Band 3 Average Distance	179	Player Load Band 3 Total Duration
50	Velocity Band 2 Average Effort Count	180	Player Load Band 4 Duration %
51	Acceleration Band 2 Average Effort Count	181	Player Load Band 4 Average Effort Count
52	Velocity Band 5 Recovery Band 4 Total No. Efforts	182	Player Load Per Metre
53	Player Load Band 6 Total Player Load	183	Velocity Band 5 Total Duration
54	Velocity Band 3 Distance Band 4 Total No. Efforts	184	Player Load Band 3 Total Player Load
55	IMA Impacts Band 3 Count	185	Player Load (1D Up %)
56	Velocity Band 4 Distance %	186	Velocity Band 6 Distance Band 3 Total No. Efforts
57	Velocity Band 3 Average Effort Count	187	Velocity Band 5 Total Distance
58	Velocity Band 2 Distance Band 4 Total No. Efforts	188	Player Load Band 4 Total Distance
59	IMA Impacts Band 4 Count	189	Acceleration Band 5 Total Duration
60	Velocity Band 4 Average Effort Count	190	Velocity Band 6 Average Distance
61	Velocity Band 3 Recovery Band 4 Total No. Efforts	191	Acceleration Band 3 Total Duration
62	IMA Impacts Band 4 Average Count	192	Player Load Band 4 Total Duration
63	Velocity Band 3 Distance %	193	Velocity Band 3 Distance Band 2 Total No. Efforts
64	Player Load Band 1 Average Duration	194	IMA Impacts Band 2 Count
65	Acceleration Band 3 Average Effort Count	195	MII Distance Interval 2
66	Velocity Band 2 Recovery Band 2 Total No. Efforts	196	Player Load Band 4 Total Player Load
67	Velocity Band 3 Duration %	197	Velocity Band 5 Recovery Band 2 Total No. Efforts
68	Average Duration	198	Effort Velocity/Duration
69	Velocity Band 5 Average Effort Count	199	Effort Acceleration/Duration
70	Velocity Band 3 Total Duration	200	Acceleration Band 1 Total Distance
71	Velocity Band 4 Recovery Band 3 Total No. Efforts	201	Player Load Band 3 Duration %
72	Velocity Band 4 Duration %	202	Velocity Band 6 Total Effort Count
73	Acceleration Band 2 Total Effort Count	203	MII Distance Interval 3
74	Velocity Band 3 Total Distance	204	Total Duration
75	Acceleration Band 2 Average Distance	205	Velocity Band 2 Distance Band 1 Total No. Efforts
76	Acceleration Band 3 Average Distance	206	Velocity Band 5 Duration %
77	Player Load Band 5 Distance %	207	Player Load Band 1 Duration %
78	Acceleration Band 5 Total Distance	208	Velocity Band 5 Recovery Band 3 Total No. Efforts
79	Acceleration Band 6 Average Effort Count	209	Velocity Band 6 Recovery Band 4 Total No. Efforts
80	Player Load Band 6 Total Distance	210	Velocity Band 2 Duration %
81	Velocity Band 4 Recovery Band 2 Total No. Efforts	211	Player Load Band 4 Total Effort Count
82	Player Load Band 2 Total Effort Count	212	MII Player Load Interval 3
83	Acceleration Band 4 Total Distance	213	Velocity Band 3 Distance Band 1 Total No. Efforts
84	Acceleration Band 6 Average Distance	214	RHIE Total Bouts
85	Player Load Band 6 Average Distance	215	Velocity Band 6 Total Distance
86	Exertion Index	216	Velocity Band 1 Duration %
87	Metabolic Power Band 1 Total Distance	217	MII Player Load Interval 2
88	Total Distance	218	Player Load (1D Side %)
89	Exertion Index Per Minute	219	Acceleration Band 6 Total Distance
90	Player Load Band 3 Average Effort Count	220	Acceleration Band 6 Total Duration
91	Velocity Band 3 Max Effort Distance	221	Age*
92	Velocity Band 6 Recovery Band 5 Total No. Efforts	222	Acceleration Band 6 Total Effort Count
93	Acceleration Band 1 Average Effort Count	223	Player Load Band 1 Total Duration
94	Velocity Band 2 Distance Band 2 Total No. Efforts	224	Acceleration Band 8 Total Distance
95	Velocity Band 3 Recovery Band 2 Total No. Efforts	225	Velocity Band 1 Total Duration
96	Player Load (1D Up)	226	Acceleration Band 3 Distance %
97	Maximum Velocity	227	Player Load Band 1 Distance %
98	Player Load (1D Fwd)	228	Acceleration Band 7 Average Distance
99	Player Load Band 2 Total Distance	229	Velocity Band 4 Recovery Band 1 Total No. Efforts

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Rank	Feature name	Rank	Feature name
100	IMA Impacts Band 5 Average Count	230	Max Acceleration
101	Total Player Load	231	Acceleration Band 3 Duration %
102	Velocity Band 4 Total Duration	232	Velocity Band 5 Distance Band 4 Total No. Efforts
103	Velocity Band 3 Distance Band 3 Total No. Efforts	233	RHIE Efforts Per Bout - Max
104	Velocity Band 2 Recovery Band 3 Total No. Efforts	234	Acceleration Density Index
105	Player Load (2D)	235	Velocity Band 5 Recovery Band 1 Total No. Efforts
106	Meterage Per Minute	236	Acceleration Band 7 Average Effort Count
107	IMA Impacts Band 1 Average Count	237	RHIE Effort Recovery - Max
108	Velocity Band 4 Total Distance	238	Velocity Band 6 Distance Band 2 Total No. Efforts
109	Player Load Band 2 Total Duration	239	Velocity Band 5 Distance %
110	Velocity Band 5 Average Distance	240	Velocity Band 1 Distance %
111	Player Load Band 3 Average Distance	241	Velocity Band 6 Distance %
112	Competition Taça*	242	Velocity Band 4 Distance Band 1 Total No. Efforts
113	Player Load Band 1 Total Distance	243	Velocity Band 2 Distance %
114	Player Load Band 5 Duration %	244	Player Position 4*
115	Acceleration Band 4 Total Duration	245	Velocity Band 6 Recovery Band 1 Total No. Efforts
116	Player Load Band 5 Total Player Load	246	Velocity Band 2 Max Effort Distance
117	Velocity Band 2 Distance Band 3 Total No. Efforts	247	Acceleration Band 8 Average Distance
118	Player Load Band 2 Total Player Load	248	Acceleration Band 6 Duration %
119	RHIE Bout Recovery - Min	249	Acceleration Band 7 Total Distance
120	MII Distance Interval 1	250	Acceleration Band 8 Total Effort Count
121	Player Load (1D Side)	251	Velocity Band 2 Recovery Band 4 Total No. Efforts
122	Player Load Band 5 Average Distance	252	Acceleration Band 7 Distance %
123	Day Week 0*	253	Acceleration Band 6 Distance %
124	MII Player Load Interval 1	254	Acceleration Band 7 Total Effort Count
125	Velocity Band 4 Distance Band 2 Total No. Efforts	255	Velocity Band 2 Recovery Band 5 Total No. Efforts
126	Velocity Band 5 Total Effort Count	256	Velocity Band 6 Recovery Band 3 Total No. Efforts
127	Player Load Band 1 Total Player Load	257	Velocity Band 6 Recovery Band 2 Total No. Efforts
128	Velocity Band 4 Recovery Band 4 Total No. Efforts	258	Acceleration Band 8 Average Effort Count
129	Player Load Band 3 Average Duration	259	No. Exercises*
130	Player Load Band 6 Total Effort Count	260	Home?*

* Descriptive parameters added by the authors.